

More on the litter crab spider *Borboropactus silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The litter crab spider *Borboropactus silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938) is endemic to South Africa and was described as *Regillus silvicola* from Port Sheptone, KwaZulu-Natal. It is now known from the Eastern Cape, Limpopo and several localities in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The general morphology of the species is noted based on photographs of live specimens. Notes on their behaviour updated distributional records, and their conservation status in South Africa are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

Numerous members of Thomisidae have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), including several *Borboropactus* specimens. The genus is recognized by its dark brown to grey bodies and legs, the strong front pair of legs with tibiae and metatarsi thick bearing a double row of strong setae. *Borboropactus* is also known for the presence of a specialized sensory region on the dorsal surface of the tarsi (Benjamin, 2011).

Borboropactus Simon, 1884 is represented by 19 species from the Oriental and Afrotropical regions (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Simon (1895) listed the genus in the Thomisidae and synonymized his *Borboropactus* Simon, 1884, with *Regillus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1884. However, *Regillus* was preoccupied and *Borboropactus* was revalidated. Wunderlich (2004) discovered members of the genus in amber and transferred the genus to Borboropactidae but that elevation was rejected by Benjamin *et al.* (2008). Benjamin (2011), using molecular data, placed *Borboropactus* within Thomisidae, sister to *Geraesta* Simon, 1889.

Eight of the *Borboropactus* species are African endemics, and three species, *B. australis* (Lawrence, 1937), *B. silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938), and *B. squalidus* Simon, 1884 are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

Borboropactus silvicola was described in 1938 from Port Sheptone, KwaZulu-Natal. Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2010) listed five new localities records, and Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2020) added 16 more. The morphology based on live specimens is discussed, and notes on their behaviour, conservation status and distribution are provided.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Requests were also made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and photographs of *B. silvicola* have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 1. *Borboropactus silvicola* female from Leggalameetse Nature Reserve, Limpopo province. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 2–9. *Borboropactus silvicola*. 2. Female habitus dorsal view. 3. Female ventral view. 4–6. Epigyne. 7–9. Male palp. Credits: 2, 3, 4–5, 7. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6, 8–9. After Lawrence (1938).

TAXONOMY

Borboropactus silvicola (Lawrence, 1938)

Regillus silvicolus Lawrence, 1938: 488

Borboropactus silvicola Roewer, 1955: 752; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023: 236; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1009; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 15, 13.

Description: TL female 7–8 mm, male 6–7 mm. Carapace dark brown, covered with dense whitish curled setae (Fig. 10) absent from the median area; longer clavate setae present on the posterior border and in the eye region (Figs 1 & 11). The carapace is narrower in the eye region (Figs 1 & 10); the fovea is longitudinal. Eyes in two rows; anterior row slightly pro-curved, posterior row very slightly recurved (Fig. 11); anterior medians larger than anterior laterals; median ocular area as wide behind than in front, longer than wide. Legs same colour as carapace with front legs directed to the front and not sideways; femora thick and inflated; tibiae and metatarsi I and II thick; with long macro setae in a double row below (Figs 2–3); legs covered by short clavate setae. Abdomen triangular, broadening towards the back; dorsally brown, without patterns; laterally paler; integument coriaceous; covered with dense, short, white clavate hairs with sparse, longer clavate setae scattered in between (Fig. 12). Epigyne: epigynal plate resembles a keyhole (Figs 4–6). Palp with a rudimentary retro tibial apophysis (Figs 7–9).

DISTRUBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Dwesa Nature Reserve (-32.27, 28.87); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.31, 29.96); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.62, 29.49); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Dlinza forest (-28.89, 31.45); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Westville (-29.82, 30.92). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Entabeni State Forest (-23.01, 30.23); Tzaneen Debengi waterfall (-23.83, 30.15). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

No photographs of *Borboropactus silvicola* on iNaturalist.

Figures 10–12. *Borboropactus silvicola* female. 10. Carapace dorsal view. 11. Eye pattern anterior view. 12. Abdomen dorsal view. Credits: Peter Webb.

LIFESTYLE

Borboropactus silvicola is a free-living ground dweller. They are usually found in leaf litter and blend in with their surroundings with their mottled colouration and general appearance. Due to the clavate setae covering their body, specimens are frequently covered with mud, and sand particles sometimes adhere to the setae.

Although they were sampled from four provinces in South Africa (Fig. 13), they are not common, and most of the specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys have been sampled from pitfall traps from the Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Forest Biomes. In the Mkambathi Nature Reserve in the Eastern Cape (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011) and Mariepskop in Mpumalanga (Taylor, 2020) the species was sampled during a yearlong survey. In the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), the second author (PW) sampled the species from decaying leaf litter in damp areas (Fig. 13). Only two specimens were listed on iNaturalist.

Figure 13. Peter Webb in the area where the species were sampled in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS

It is presently known from four South African provinces and protected in seven protected areas. There are no known threats and is listed as Least Concern.

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